

Structural, Thermal and Electrical Studies on Manganese-, Iron-, Cobalt-, Nickel- and Copper(II) Polychelates

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Polychelates of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with Schiff base ligand derived from 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl-biphenyl and 2,3-butanedione dihydrazone have been prepared having 1 : 1 (M : L) stoichiometry. The Mn^{II}, Fe^{II} and Co^{II} polychelates are of six-coordinated octahedral structure, while the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} polychelates have distorted octahedral geometry. The ligand field and nephelauxetic parameters have been determined from the spectra, using ligand-field theory of spin-allowed transition.

The interaction between metal ions and bridging ligands may lead to the formation of coordination polymers in which the chelated metal ions are bridged by ligand molecules. The formation of a macromolecular chain may be expected for a ligand with two chelating sites, which for steric reasons can not interact with the same metal ions. The present communication describes the synthesis and characterisation of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} polychelates of the quadridentate ligand 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl-biphenyl-2,3-butanedione dihydrazone [DDBBD].

Results and Discussion

All the polychelates (Table 1) are coloured amorphous solids and insoluble in water and common organic solvents. The elemental analyses suggest 1 : 1 metal : ligand stoichiometry.

The ir spectrum of the ligands shows a sharp strong band at 1 595 cm⁻¹ (C=N) which shifted to lower frequency by 8–25 cm⁻¹ in polychelates, suggesting the coordination to the central metal atom through the nitrogen of the azomethine group¹. The ligand exhibits a medium broad band at 2 920 cm⁻¹ assignable to intramolecularly hydro-

gen bonded OH stretch². The polychelates do not show ν_{OH} group frequency thereby indicating that OH group of the ligand is utilised in the formation of M–O bond. This is further supported by the shift of C–O frequency from 1 330 to 1 390 cm⁻¹ in these polychelates³. The ligand band at 920 cm⁻¹ (N–N) shifts to higher frequency by 15–45 cm⁻¹ upon chelation. The magnitude of this shift indicates the monodentate coordination⁴ of the N–N residue, as a shift of >50 cm⁻¹ is usually observed in bidentate coordination. A shift to a higher frequency in ν_{N-N} is expected due to the reduction of the lone-pair repulsive forces of the adjacent nitrogen atoms⁵. A band found at 540–590 cm⁻¹ in polychelates is ascribed to ν_{M-O} vibrations and a band at 450–500 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ν_{M-N} ⁶. The weak broad bands observed in the chelates at 3 300–3 450 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to ν_{OH} of water molecules⁶. The Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} chelates also exhibit sharp peaks at around 1 560 and 830 cm⁻¹ assignable to the presence of coordinated water molecules⁷.

The electronic spectrum of the Mn^{II} polychelate shows three weak bands at 13 880, 17 850 and 22 720 cm⁻¹ which have been assigned to transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$, 4E_g respectively, in an octahedral field of Mn^{II} ion^{8,9}. The observed magnetic moment of the Mn^{II} chelate (6.06 B.M.) is slightly greater than the spin-only value (5.92 B.M.), but within the limits of spin-free values for five unpaired electrons indicating that the polymer is high-spin octahedral¹⁰. The Fe^{II} polychelate shows a doublets band at 10 000–12 000, shoulder at 14 700 and 20 830 cm⁻¹, assigned to ${}^5T_{2g}(D) \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ and $t_{2g} \rightarrow \pi^*$ or charge transfer transitions respectively. Cotton and Meyers¹¹ suggested that such doublet bands in six-coordinated Fe^{II} complexes could be due to either Jahn-Teller distortion or D_{4h} . Crystal field parameters and nephelauxetic ratio have been calculated¹² for the iron polychelate : $D_q = 1 052 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 560 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.536$ and $C = 2 274 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. These values are in favour of tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry of Fe^{II} polychelate which is consistent with the results reported by Shah and Shah¹³.

TABLE 1—THERMAL AND ELECTRICAL DATA OF DDBBD POLYCHELATES

Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	J $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} (\text{K})$	E_a eV
Mn ^{II} -DDBBD	265	2.930×10^{-10} (313)	0.637
		1.189×10^{-9} (373)	
		5.948×10^{-8} (513)	
Fe ^{II} -DDBBD	280	5.750×10^{-11} (303)	0.248
		8.511×10^{-11} (373)	
		7.940×10^{-10} (513)	
Co ^{II} -DDBBD	330	8.831×10^{-12} (303)	0.397
		3.336×10^{-11} (373)	
		7.506×10^{-10} (515)	
Ni ^{II} -DDBBD	305	9.870×10^{-12} (312)	0.564
		3.657×10^{-11} (373)	
		1.007×10^{-9} (512)	
Cu ^{II} -DDBBD	270	4.134×10^{-9} (313)	0.447
		9.096×10^{-9} (373)	
		1.895×10^{-9} (513)	

The reduction of B values upon chelation indicates that a small amount of the σ and π electron density on the metal may be transferred on to the ligand, and such delocalisation will increase the mean distance between d -electrons and thereby reduce B . In other words, a decrease in B value suggests the partial covalent nature of the M-L bond¹⁴. The magnetic moment of the Fe^{II} polychelate (6.14 B.M.) suggests a high-spin octahedral geometry. The higher value of magnetic moment can be attributed to the steric volume of the bulky ligand causing an increase in M-L bond distance thereby decreasing D_q sufficiently enough to alter the ground state to the high-spin $^5T_{2g}$ ^{12,14}. In the Co^{II} polychelate, two bands at 9 250 and 20 830 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3). However, the $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) is not clear, since it is a two-electron process and has a much lower oscillator strength than the other two transitions and is therefore much weaker^{15,16}. The values of $D_q = 1047 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 852 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.760$, $\beta^0 = 23.92\%$, $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.63$ and $\nu_2 = 19733 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, calculated using Bauhausen equation¹⁷, lie within the limit reported for octahedral Co^{II} complexes⁶. The observed magnetic moment of Co^{II} polychelate (5.33 B.M.) is in good agreement with high-spin octahedral geometry. Since, spin-only value for three unpaired electron is only 3.99 B.M., the high value in the present case may be attributed to high-spin orbital contribution¹⁸. The electronic spectrum of the Ni^{II} polychelate shows three $d-d$ transition bands at 9 800, 13 880 and 23 800 cm^{-1} corresponding to the transitions $^3B_{1g} \rightarrow ^3B_{2g}$, $^3B_{1g} \rightarrow ^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively, which are in the range required for the spin-free octahedral Ni^{II} chelates^{17,19}. This structure is further supported by the ratio of ν_2/ν_1 is (1.4) which is close to the value expected for a distorted octahedral structure¹². The Racah parameters $D_q = 980 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B_{35} = 551 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.51$, $\beta^0 = 48\%$, $\nu_2 = 14730 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_3 = 22930 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.41$ have been obtained using diagonal sum value²¹. Low values of the B and β suggest appreciable amount of the covalent character in the metal-ligand bonds. It is possible to calculate $Dt = 69 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $Dq^{xy} = 1041$ and $Dq^z = 919 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The magnetic moment of Ni^{II} polychelate (3.63 B.M.) is higher than the spin-only value for octahedral stereochemistry. Higher value of magnetic moment in the present case may be due to the departure from octahedral geometry towards tetragonal (D_{4h}) geometry²². The diffuse reflectance spectrum of the Cu^{II} polychelate contains two bands at 13 510–14 280 and 10 410 cm^{-1} in their normally expected region for square-planar Cu^{II} chelates²³. A broad band at about 13 510 cm^{-1} suggests a distorted octahedral geometry²⁴, which may be assigned to $^2B_1 \rightarrow ^2B_{2g}$ and $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2A_{1g}$ transitions respectively. The magnetic moment of the Cu^{II} polychelate (1.92 B.M.) is very close to the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) expected for one unpaired electron which offers the possibility of oc-

tahedral geometry²⁵.

In the thermograms weight-losses of the Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} polychelates in the range 180–230° are 9.02, 8.90, 9.40 and 8.80% respectively, corresponding to two coordinated water molecules per repeating unit of the polychelate²⁶. The Cu^{II} polychelate show a weight-loss of 9.10% around 130° corresponding to two crystal water molecules²⁷. The observed higher weight-loss than that required may be due to some other chain degradation reaction involved in pyrolysis of the chelates²⁸. From the procedural decomposition temperature (Table 1), it can be concluded that the thermal stability order of the polychelates is Co > Ni > Fe > Cu > Mn. The analysis of thermogram (Fig. 1) indicates that the polychelates decompose in two stages after loss of water molecules. In all the chelates, the rate of decomposition in the first stage is slow as compared to the second stage and decomposition completes at about 600°.

The coordination polymers are known for their behaviour as semiconductors. In the electrical conduction domain, the temperature dependences of the electrical conductivity obey the equation²⁹, $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/KT)$, where K is the Boltzmann constant, σ the electrical conductivity at temperature $T = T$, σ_0 the electrical conductivity at temperature $T = \infty$, E_a the activation energy of electrical conduction and T the absolute temperature. In the present study temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity exhibits two distinct regions. In low temperature region (Fig. 2), the slopes of the plots have small values. This may be due to extrinsic conduction present in them³⁰, whereas in high temperature region, a linear relationship with high value of $\log \sigma = F(10^3/T)$ has been observed. In this temperature domain these polychelates may behave as intrinsic semiconductors³⁰. The electrical conductivity of these polychelates increases in the order : Mn > Cu > Fe > Ni >

Fig. 1. Decomposition pattern of representative polymer.

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of $\log \sigma$.

Co at 100° , and the activation energy of electrical conduction increased in the order: Mn > Ni > Cu > Co > Fe. The values of electrical conductivity and activation energy vary with the ionisation tendency³¹ of the metal ions in the polychelates.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade and double-distilled solvents were used.

4,4'-Dihydrazone-3,3'-diacetylbiophenyl (DDABP) and 2,3-butanedione dihydrazone (BDDH) were prepared by known methods^{32,33}.

Preparation of polychelates: Equimolar amounts of the metal acetate and ligand DDBBD (dissolved and filtered separately in 25–30 ml of DMF) were mixed in hot condition with stirring. The mixture was refluxed at 135° for 4–6 h. The resulting products were filtered, washed successively with DMF, dry ethanol and acetone and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused CaCl_2 . All the polychelates gave satisfactory C, H, N and metal analyses.

C, H and N analyses were made on a Coleman analyser. The metal content was determined by oxide method³⁴. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as a calibrant and the values were corrected for diamagnetism. Diffuse reflectance spectra were measured on a Karl-Zeiss VSU-2p spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. TG analysis was carried out on a Perkin-Elmer thermobalance at a heating rate 10° per min in air and using Pt-Rh thermocouple. The direct current conductivity of the polychelate (1.20 cm dia \times 0.25–0.30 cm pellet) was measured over a temperature range 300–520 K using BPL-India Million RM-160 MK IIIA megohmmeter and TF-2700 universal bridge in air.

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